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Stránky českých a slovenských malakologů

Check-list and distribution maps of the molluscs of the Czech and Slovak Republics

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The current version of the check-list follows HORSÁK et al. (2013) with up-to-date modifications supplemented with a reference. Distribution map for each species was constructed based on published data and our knowledge based on unpublished records. So far 252 species of molluscs, including 223 species of gastropods (52 aquatic and 171 terrestrial) and 29 species of bivalves, have been found outdoors in the Czech Republic. The fauna of Slovakia comprises 261 species, including 231 gastropods (57 aquatic and 174 terrestrial) and 30 bivalves.

Abbreviations:

To the checklist:

B – Bohemia;

M – Moravia (incl. Czech Silesia);

S – Slovakia;

† – an extinct species for the territory;

(†) – probably extinct species for the territory;

+ – a non-native species for the territory;

! – an endemic species of smaller area.

? – occurrence probable, but not confirmed.

To the maps:

M – past distribution;

R – recent distribution;

M<R – number of occurrences increased over the last few decades (e.g. for non-native species);

M>R – number of occurrences declined over the last few decades (e.g. for seriously threatened species);

M=R – no obvious changes in the species distribution.

Updates to [HORSÁK et al. \(2013\)](#) are marked with an asterisk * and annotated below the species list. There is also a handy tiptool with comments on the names of the changed species (only available in operating systems with a mouse pointer; not in smartphones).

GASTROPODA

plži

subclass Neritimorpha

order Cycloneritida

Neritidae

zubovcovití

Theodoxus Montfort, 1810

<i>T. danubialis</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	–	M	S	map images	zubovec dunajský
<i>T. fluviatilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B†	–	+S	map images	zubovec říční
<i>T. transversalis</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	–	–	S	map images	zubovec pruhovaný

subclass Caenogastropoda

order Architaenioglossa

Viviparidae

bahenkovití

Viviparus Montfort, 1810

<i>V. acerosus</i> Bourguignat, 1862 *	+B	M	S	map images	bahenka uherská
<i>V. contectus</i> (Millet, 1813)	B	M	S	map images	bahenka živorodá
<i>V. viviparus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	+M	–	map images	bahenka pruhovaná

Aciculidae

jehlovkovití

Acicula Hartmann, 1821

<i>A. parcelineata</i> (Clessin, 1911)	–	M	S	map images	jehlička malinká
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Platyla Moquin-Tandon, 1856

<i>P. polita</i> (Hartmann, 1840)	B	M	S	images	jehlovka hladká
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unassigned order of
Caenogastropoda

Melanopsidae

piskořkovití

Esperiana Bourguignat, 1877

<i>E. daudebartii acicularis</i> (A. Férussac, 1823)	–	–	S	map images	piskořka ostrá
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<i>E. esperi</i> (A. Férussac, 1823)	–	–	S	map images	piskořka skvrnitá
Thiaridae Gill, 1871 (1823)					věžovkovití
<i>Melanoides</i> Olivier, 1804					
<i>M. tuberculata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	–	+M	+S	map images	věžovka hrbolkatá
order Littorinimorpha					
Bithyniidae					bahňvkvití
<i>Bithynia</i> Leach, 1818					
<i>B. leachii</i> (Sheppard, 1823)	–	M	S	map images	bahňvka nadmutá
<i>B. tentaculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	bahňvka rmutná
<i>B. transsilvanica</i> (Bielz, 1853)	+B	M	S	map images	bahňvka východní
Bythinellidae					praménkovití
<i>Bythinella</i> Moquin-Tandon, 1856					
<i>B. austriaca</i> (von Frauenfeld, 1857)	B	M	S	map images	praménka rakouská
<i>B. pannonica</i> (von Frauenfeld, 1865)	–	–	S!	map images	praménka široká
Hydrobiidae					zdrojenkovití
<i>Clathrocaspia</i> Lindholm, 1930					
<i>C. knipowitschii</i> (Makarov, 1938) *	–	–	+S	map images	mřížovka kaspická
<i>Alzoniella</i> Giusti & Bodon, 1984					
<i>A. slovenica</i> (Ložek & Brtek, 1964)	–	M!	S!	map images	vývěrka slovenská
<i>Hauffenia</i> Pollonera, 1889					
<i>H. kissdalmae</i> Eröss & Petró, 2008 *	–	–	S!	map images	krasovka Kissova
<i>H. lozekiana</i> Haase, Grego, Eröss, Farkas & Fehér, 2021 *	–	–	S!	map images	krasovka Ložkova
Lithoglyphidae					kamolepovití
<i>Lithoglyphus</i> Menke, 1830					
<i>L. naticoides</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	–	M	S	map images	kamolep říční
Tateidae					písečníkovití
<i>Potamopyrgus</i> W. Stimpson, 1865					

<i>P. antipodarum</i> (J. E. Gray, 1843)	+B	+M	+S	map images	písečník novozélandský
subclass Heterobranchia					
infraclass "Lower Heterobranchia"					
Valvatidae točenkovití					
<i>Valvata</i> O. F. Müller, 1773					
<i>V. cristata</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	B	M	S	map images	točenka plochá
<i>V. macrostoma</i> Mörch, 1864	B	–	S	map images	točenka veleústá
<i>V. piscinalis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	točenka kulovitá
<i>Borysthenia</i> Lindholm, 1914					
<i>B. naticina</i> (Menke, 1845)	–	–	S	map images	zákrutka říční
superorder Hygrophila					
Acroloxidae člunicovití					
<i>Acroloxus</i> Beck, 1838					
<i>A. lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	člunice jezerní
Lymnaeidae plovatkovití					
<i>Myxas</i> J. Sowerby, 1822					
<i>M. glutinosa</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B†	–	–	map images	pláštěnka sliznatá
<i>Radix</i> Montfort, 1810					
<i>R. auricularia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	uchatka nadmutá
<i>Ampullaceana</i> Servain, 1882					
<i>A. ampla</i> (Hartmann, 1821) *	B	M	S	map images	baňatka široká
<i>A. balthica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) *	B	M	S	map images	baňatka vejčitá
<i>A. lagotis</i> (Schrank, 1803) *	B	M	S	map images	baňatka zaostřená
<i>Peregriana</i> Servain, 1882					
<i>P. peregra</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	B	M	S	map images	potočnatka toulavá
<i>Galba</i> Schrank, 1803					
<i>G. truncatula</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	bahnatka malá
<i>Pseudosuccinea</i> F. C. Baker, 1908 *					
<i>P. columella</i> (Say, 1817) *	+B	–	–	map images	blátivka americká
<i>Ladislavella</i> Dybowski, 1913 *					

* <i>L. occulta</i> (Jackiewicz, 1959)	B	M	S	map images	blatnatka severní
<i>Stagnicola</i> Jeffreys, 1830					
<i>S. corvus</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	B	M	S	map images	blatenka tmavá
<i>S. fuscus</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1821)	B	–	–	map images	blatenka rybničná
<i>S. palustris</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	B	M	S	map images	blatenka bažinná
<i>Lymnaea</i> Lamarck, 1799					
<i>L. stagnalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	plovatka bahenní
Physidae					levatkovití
<i>Aplexa</i> Fleming, 1820					
<i>A. hypnorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	levotočka bažinná
<i>Physa</i> Draparnaud, 1801					
<i>P. acuta</i> Draparnaud, 1805 *	+B	+M	+S	map images	levatka ostrá
<i>P. fontinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	levatka říční
Planorbidae					okružákovití
<i>Planorbella</i> Haldeman, 1843					
<i>P. duryi</i> (Wetherby, 1879) *	–	–	+S	map images	okružík floridský
<i>Planorbis</i> O. F. Müller, 1773					
<i>P. carinatus</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	B	M	S	map images	terčovník kýlnatý
<i>P. planorbis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	terčovník vroubený
<i>Anisus</i> Studer, 1820					
<i>A. leucostoma</i> (Millet, 1813)	B	M	S	map images	svinutec běloústý
<i>A. septemgyratus</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	–	M	S	map images	svinutec sedmitočný
<i>A. spirorbis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	svinutec kruhovitý
<i>A. vortex</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	svinutec zploštělý
<i>A. vorticulus</i> (Troschel, 1834)	B	M	S	map images	svinutec tenký
<i>Bathyomphalus</i> Charpentier, 1837					
<i>B. contortus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	řemeník svinutý
<i>Gyraulus</i> Charpentier, 1837					
<i>G. acronicus</i> (A. Férussac, 1807)	B	M	S	map images	kružník severní

<i>G. albus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	kružník bělavý
<i>G. crista</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	kružník žebrovaný
<i>G. parvus</i> (Say, 1817) *	B	M	S	map images	kružník malý
<i>G. riparius</i> (Westerlund, 1865)	–	–	S	map images	kružník drobný
<i>G. rossmaessleri</i> (Auerswald, 1852) *	B	M	S	map images	kružník Rossmuesslerův
<i>Hippeutis</i> Charpentier, 1837					
<i>H. complanatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	kýlnatec čočkovitý
<i>Segmentina</i> Fleming, 1818					
<i>S. nitida</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	lištovka lesklá
<i>Ancylus</i> O. F. Müller, 1773					
<i>A. fluviatilis</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	B	M	S	map images	kamomil říční
<i>Planorbarius</i> Duméril, 1806					
<i>P. corneus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	okružák ploský
<i>Menetus</i> H. & A. Adams, 1855					
<i>M. dilatatus</i> (Gould, 1841)	+B	–	–	map images	menetovník rozšířený
<i>Ferrissia</i> Walker, 1903					
<i>F. californica</i> (Rowell, 1863) *	+B	+M	+S	map images	člunka pravohrotá
superorder Eupulmonata					
order Ellobiida					
Ellobiidae					
elobiovití					
<i>Carychium</i> O. F. Müller, 1773					
<i>C. minimum</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	B	M	S	images	síměnka nejmenší
<i>C. tridentatum</i> (Risso, 1826)	B	M	S	images	síměnka trojzubá
order Stylommatophora					
Succineidae					
jantarkovití					
<i>Succinea</i> Draparnaud, 1801					
<i>S. putris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	images	jantarka obecná
<i>Oxyloma</i> Westerlund, 1885					
<i>O. elegans</i> (Risso, 1826)	B	M	S	images	jantarovka úhledná
<i>Succinella</i> Mabilie, 1871					
<i>S. oblonga</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	jantařička podlouhlá

Quickella C. Boettger, 1939

Q. arenaria (Potiez & Michaud, 1838) – – S [map](#) [images](#) jantarenka písečná
Chondrinidae ovsenkovití

Abida Turton, 1831

A. secale (Draparnaud, 1801) – – S [map](#) [images](#) žitenka rezná

Granaria Held, 1838

G. frumentum (Draparnaud, 1801) B M S [images](#) žitovka obilná

Chondrina Reichenbach, 1828

C. avenacea (Bruguière, 1792) B – – [images](#) ovsenka skalní

C. arcadica clienta (Westerlund, 1883) B M S [map](#) [images](#) ovsenka žebnatá

C. tatrica Ložek, 1948 – – S! [map](#) [images](#) ovsenka karpatská

Truncatellinidae

drobničkovití

Columella Westerlund, 1878

C. aspera Waldén, 1966 B M S [map](#) [images](#) ostroústka drsná

C. columella (G. von Martens, 1830) – – S [map](#) [images](#) ostroústka válcovitá

C. edentula (Draparnaud, 1805) B M S [images](#) ostroústka bezzubá

Truncatellina Lowe, 1852

T. claustralis (Gredler, 1856) B M S [map](#) [images](#) drobnička jižní

T. costulata (Nilsson, 1823) B M S [map](#) [images](#) drobnička žebnatá

T. cylindrica (A. Férussac, 1807) B M S [images](#) drobnička válcovitá

Argnidae

válcovkovití

Argna Cossmann, 1889

A. bielzi (Rossmässler, 1859) – – S [map](#) [images](#) válcovka karpatská

Cochlicopidae

oblovkovití

Cochlicopa A. Férussac, 1821

C. lubrica (O. F. Müller, 1774) B M S [images](#) oblovka lesklá

C. lubricella (Porro, 1838) B M S [images](#) oblovka drobná

C. nitens (M. von Gallenstein, 1848) B M S [map](#) [images](#) oblovka slatinná

Enidae

hladovkovití

Chondrula Beck, 1837

<i>C. tridens</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	trojzubka stepní
<i>Ena</i> Turton, 1831					
<i>E. montana</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	hladovka horská
<i>Merdigera</i> Held, 1838					
<i>M. obscura</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	kalonoska chlumní
<i>Zebrina</i> Held, 1838					
<i>Z. detrita</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	lačník stepní
Orculidae					
sudovkovití					
<i>Orcula</i> Held, 1838					
<i>O. dolium</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	–	M	S	map images	sudovka skalní
<i>Sphyradium</i> Charpentier, 1837					
<i>S. doliolum</i> (Bruguière, 1792)	B	M	S	images	soudkovka žebertatá
Pagodulinidae					
včelínkovití					
<i>Pagodulina</i> Clessin, 1876					
<i>P. pagodula</i> (Des Moulins, 1830)	–	M	S	map images	včelínka ozdobná
Pupillidae					
zrnovkovití					
<i>Pupilla</i> Fleming, 1828					
<i>P. alpicola</i> (Charpentier, 1837) *	B	M	S	map images	zrnovka alpská
<i>P. muscorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	images	zrnovka mechová
<i>P. sterrii</i> (von Voith, 1840) *	B	M	S	images	zrnovka žebertatá
<i>P. triplicata</i> (Studer, 1820)	B	M	S	images	zrnovka třízubá
Pyramidulidae					
kuželovkovití					
<i>Pyramidula</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>P. pusilla</i> (Vallot, 1801) *	B	M	S	map images	kuželovka skalní
<i>P. saxatilis</i> (Hartmann, 1842) *	–	–	S	map images	kuželovka horská
Spelaeodiscidae					
trojníčkovití					
<i>Spelaeodiscus</i> Brusina, 1886					
<i>S. triarius tatricus</i> (Hazay, 1883)	–	–	S!	map images	trojníček tatranský
Valloniidae					
údolníčkovití					
<i>Vallonia</i> Risso, 1826					

<i>V. costata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	údolníček žebernatý
<i>V. pulchella</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	B	M	S	images	údolníček drobný
<i>Acanthinula</i> Beck, 1847					
<i>A. aculeata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	ostnatka trnitá
Vertiginidae					vrkočovití
<i>Vertigo</i> O. F. Müller, 1773					
<i>V. alpestris</i> Alder, 1838	B	M	S	images	vrkoč horský
<i>V. angustior</i> Jeffreys, 1830	B	M	S	map images	vrkoč útlý
<i>V. antivertigo</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	vrkoč mnohozubý
<i>V. geyeri</i> Lindholm, 1925	B	M	S	map images	vrkoč Geyerův
<i>V. hoppii</i> (Møller, 1842) *	–	–	S	map images	vrkoč severní
<i>V. lilljeborgi</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	B	M	–	map images	vrkoč rašelinný
<i>V. moulinsiana</i> (Dupuy, 1849)	B	M	S	map images	vrkoč bažinný
<i>V. pusilla</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	B	M	S	images	vrkoč lesní
<i>V. pygmaea</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	vrkoč malinký
<i>V. ronnebyensis</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	B	–	–	map images	vrkoč nordický
<i>V. substriata</i> (Jeffreys, 1833)	B	M	S	images	vrkoč rýhovaný
Clausiliidae					závornatkovití
<i>Alopi</i> H. & A. Adams, 1855					
<i>A. bielzi clathrata</i> (E. A. Bielz, 1856)	–	–	S!	map images	sivěnka ozdobná
<i>Cochlodina</i> A. Férussac, 1821					
<i>C. cerata</i> (Rossmässler, 1836)	–	M!	S	map images	vřetenovka vosková
<i>C. costata</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	B	M	–	images	vřetenovka zaměňená
<i>C. dubiosa corcontica</i> Brabenec, 1967	B!	–	–	images	vřetenovka krkonošská
<i>C. fimbriata</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	–	–	S	map images	vřetenovka skrytá
<i>C. laminata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	B	M	S	images	vřetenovka hladká
<i>C. orthostoma</i> (Menke, 1828)	B	M	S	images	vřetenovka rovnoústá
<i>Charpentieria</i> Stabile, 1864					

<i>C. ornata</i> (Rossmässler, 1836)	B	M	–	images	zdobenka tečkovaná
<i>Ruthenica</i> Lindholm, 1924					
<i>R. filograna</i> (Rossmässler, 1836)	B	M	S	images	žebernatěnka drobná
<i>Pseudofusulus</i> H. Nordsieck, 1977					
<i>P. varians</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	B	M†	S	map images	vřetenec horský
<i>Macrogastrea</i> Hartmann, 1841					
<i>M. badia</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	B	M	–	map images	řasnatka tmavá
<i>M. borealis</i> (Boettger, 1878) *	–	M	S	map images	řasnatka žebernatá
<i>M. plicatula</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	řasnatka lesní
<i>M. tumida</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	B	M	S	images	řasnatka nadmutá
<i>M. ventricosa</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	řasnatka břichatá
<i>Clausilia</i> Draparnaud, 1805					
<i>C. bidentata</i> (Strøm, 1765)	B	–	–	map images	závornatka černavá
<i>C. cruciata</i> (Studer, 1820)	B	M	S	images	závornatka křížatá
<i>C. dubia</i> Draparnaud, 1805	B	M	S	images	závornatka drsná
<i>C. pumila</i> C. Pfeiffer, 1828	B	M	S	images	závornatka kyjovitá
<i>C. rugosa</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	závornatka malá
<i>Laciniaria</i> Hartmann, 1842					
<i>L. plicata</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	mnohozubka evropská
<i>Alinda</i> H. & A. Adams, 1855					
<i>A. biplicata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	B	M	S	images	vřetenatka obecná
<i>Balea</i> Gray, J. E. 1824					
<i>B. perversa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	images	hrotice obrácená
<i>Pseudalinda</i> Boettger, 1877					
<i>P. stabilis</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1847)	–	–	S	map images	vrutenka karpatská
<i>Vestia</i> Hesse, 1916					

<i>V. elata</i> (Rossmässler, 1836)	–	–	S	images	nádolka vyyvýšená
<i>V. gulo</i> (E. A. Bielz, 1859)	–	M	S	map images	nádolka hrubá
<i>V. ranojevici moravica</i> (Brabenec, 1952)	–	M!	–	map images	nádolka moravská
<i>V. turgida</i> (Rossmässler, 1836)	B	M	S	images	nádolka nadmutá
<i>Bulgarica</i> O. Boettger, 1877					
<i>B. cana</i> (Held, 1836)	B	M	S	images	vřetenka šedivá
<i>B. nitidosa</i> (Uličný, 1893)	B!	–	–	images	vřetenka lesklá
Ferussaciidae					
bezočkovití					
<i>Cecilioides</i> A. Férussac, 1814					
<i>C. acicula</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	bezočka šídlovitá
<i>C. petitiiana</i> (Benoit, 1862)	–	–	+S	map images	bezočka středomořská
Punctidae					
boděnkovití					
<i>Punctum</i> Morse, 1864					
<i>P. pygmaeum</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	map images	boděnka malinká
Helicodiscidae					
spirálníčkovití					
<i>Lucilla</i> R. T. Lowe, 1852					
* <i>L. scintilla</i> (R. T. Lowe, 1852)	+B	+M	+S	map images	spirálovníček zemní
<i>L. singleyana</i> (Pilsbry, 1889)	–	–	+S	map images	spirálovníček bílý
Discidae					
vrásenkovití					
<i>Discus</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>D. ruderatus</i> (Hartmann, 1821)	B	M	S	images	vrásenka pomezní
<i>Gonyodiscus</i> Fitzinger, 1833 *					
<i>G. perspectivus</i> (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1816) *	B	M	S	images	vrásník orlojovitý
<i>G. rotundatus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	B	M	S	images	vrásník okrouhlý
Gastrodontidae					
zemounkovití					
<i>Aegopinella</i> Lindholm, 1927					
<i>A. epipedostoma iuncta</i> Hudec, 1964	–	M	S	images	sítovka podhorská
<i>A. minor</i> (Stabile, 1864)	B	M	S	images	sítovka suchomilná

<i>A. nitens</i> (Michaud, 1831)	B	M	S	images	sítovka blyštivá
<i>A. nitidula</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	M	–	images	sítovka lesklá
<i>A. pura</i> (Alder, 1830)	B	M	S	images	sítovka čistá
<i>A. ressmanni</i> (Westerlund, 1883)	B	–	–	map images	sítovka dravá
<i>Perpolita</i> H. B. Baker, 1928 *					
<i>P. hammonis</i> (Strøm, 1765) *	B	M	S	images	blyštivka rýhovaná
<i>P. petronella</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) *	B	M	S	images	blyštivka skleněná
<i>P. radiatella hesperia</i> Saito & Nekola, 2025 *	B	M	S	map images	blyštivka netušená
<i>Zonitoides</i> Lehmann, 1862					
<i>Z. arboreus</i> (Say, 1817)	–	+M	–	map images	zemounek lesní
<i>Z. nitidus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	zemounek lesklý
Oxychilidae skelnatkovití					
<i>Oxychilus</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>O. alliarius</i> (Miller, 1822)	B	–	–	map images	skelnatka česneková
<i>O. cellarius</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	skelnatka drnová
<i>O. depressus</i> (Sterki, 1880)	B	M	S	images	skelnatka stlačená
<i>O. deubeli</i> (A. J. Wagner, 1914)	–	–	S	map images	skelnatka východní
<i>O. draparnaudi</i> (Beck, 1837)	+B	+M	+S	images	skelnatka západní
<i>O. glaber</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	B	M	S	images	skelnatka hladká
<i>O. hydatinus</i> (Rossmässler, 1838)	–	–	+S	map images	skelnatka malá
<i>O. inopinatus</i> (Uličný, 1887)	B	M	S	images	skelnatka zemní
<i>O. mortilleti</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1859)	B(†)	–	–	map images	skelnatka horská
<i>Carpathica</i> A. J. Wagner, 1895					
<i>C. calophana</i> (Westerlund, 1881)	–	–	S	map images	sklovitka karpatská
<i>Daudebardia</i> Hartmann, 1821					
<i>D. brevipes</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	M	S	images	sklovatka krátkonohá
<i>D. rufa</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	M	S	map images	sklovatka rudá

Pristilomatidae					skelničkovití
<i>Vitreia</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>V. contracta</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	B	M	S	images	skelnička stažená
<i>V. crystallina</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	skelnička průhledná
<i>V. diaphana</i> (Studer, 1820)	B	M	S	images	skelnička průzračná
<i>V. subrimata</i> (Reinhardt, 1871)	B	M	S	images	skelnička zjizvená
<i>V. transsylvanica</i> (Clessin, 1877)	B	M	S	map images	skelnička karpatská
Euconulidae					kuželíkovití
<i>Euconulus</i> Reinhardt, 1883					
<i>E. alderi</i> (J. E. Gray, 1840) *	B	M	S	images	kuželík tmavý
<i>E. fulvus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	kuželík drobný
Zonitidae					zemounovití
<i>Aegopis</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>A. verticillus</i> (Lamarck, 1822)	B	M	–	images	zemoun skalní
Milacidae					plžicovití
<i>Tandonia</i> Lessona & Pollonera, 1882					
<i>T. budapestensis</i> (Hazay, 1880)	B	M	S	map images	plžice štíhlá
* <i>T. kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1931)	–	–	+S	map images	plžice balkánská
<i>T. rustica</i> (Millet, 1843) *	B	–	–	map images	plžice vroubená
Agriolimacidae					slimáčkovití
<i>Deroceras</i> Rafinesque, 1820					
<i>D. agreste</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	map images	slimáček polní
<i>D. invadens</i> Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011 *	+B	+M	+S	map images	slimáček invazní
<i>D. juranum</i> Wüthrich, 1993 *	B	–	–	map images	slimáček jurský
<i>D. laeve</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	slimáček hladký
<i>D. praecox</i> Wiktor, 1966	B	M	S	map images	slimáček lesní
<i>D. reticulatum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	map images	slimáček sítkovaný
<i>D. rodnae</i> Grossu & Lupu, 1965	B	M	S	map images	slimáček světlý
<i>D. sturanyi</i> (Simroth, 1894)	B	M	S	map images	slimáček evropský

<i>D. turcicum</i> (Simroth, 1894)	B	M	S	map images	slimáček balkánský
<i>Krynickillus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851					
<i>K. melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851 *	+B	+M	+S	map images	slimáčkovec černohlavý
Boettgerillidae					
bledničkovití					
<i>Boettgerilla</i> Simroth, 1910					
<i>B. pallens</i> Simroth, 1912	+B	+M	+S	images	blednička útlá
Limacidae					
slimákovití					
<i>Ambigolimax</i> Pollonera, 1887					
<i>A. valentianus</i> (A. Férussac, 1821) *	–	–	+S	map images	paslimák iberský
<i>Bielzia</i> Clessin, 1887					
<i>B. coeruleans</i> (M. Bielz, 1851)	–	M	S	map images	modranka karpatská
<i>Limax</i> Linnaeus, 1758					
<i>L. cinereoniger</i> Wolf, 1803	B	M	S	images	slimák popelavý
<i>L. maximus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	B	M	S	images	slimák největší
<i>Limacus</i> Lehmann, 1864					
<i>L. flavus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	+B	+M	S	map images	slimákovec pestrý
<i>L. maculatus</i> (Kaleniczenko, 1851) *	–	+M	–	map images	slimákovec skvrnitý
<i>Malacolimax</i> Malm, 1868					
<i>M. tenellus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	plžík žlutý
<i>Lehmanna</i> Heynemann, 1863					
<i>L. carpatica</i> Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022 *	–	M	S	map images	podkornatka tečkovaná
<i>L. macroflagellata</i> Grossu & Lupu, 1962	B	M	S	map images	podkornatka karpatská
<i>L. marginata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	podkornatka žíhaná
Vitrinidae					
skleněnkovití					
<i>Semilimax</i> Gray, J. E. 1847					
<i>S. kotulae</i> (Westerlund, 1883)	B	M	S	images	slimáčník horský
<i>S. semilimax</i> (J. Férussac, 1802)	B	M	S	images	slimáčník táhlý
<i>Eucobresia</i> H. B. Baker, 1929					

<i>E. diaphana</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	M	S	images	slimáčnice průhledná
<i>E. nivalis</i> (Dumont & Mortillet, 1854)	B	M	S	images	slimáčnice lesní
<i>Vitrina</i> Draparnaud, 1801					
<i>V. pellucida</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	skleněnka průsvitná
Arionidae					
plzákovití					
<i>Arion</i> A. Férussac, 1819					
<i>A. circumscriptus</i> Johnston, 1828	B	M	–	images	plzák žíhaný
<i>A. distinctus</i> Mabilie, 1868	B	M	S	images	plzák zahradní
<i>A. fasciatus</i> (Nilsson, 1823)	B	M	S	images	plzák žlutopruhý
<i>A. fuscus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	plzák hnědý
<i>A. intermedius</i> Normand, 1852 *	B	M	+S	map images	plzák nejmenší
<i>A. obesoductus</i> Reischütz, 1973	B	M	–	map images	plzák alpský
<i>A. rufus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	images	plzák lesní
<i>A. silvaticus</i> Lohmander, 1937	B	M	S	images	plzák hajní
<i>A. vulgaris</i> Moquin-Tandon, 1855	+B	+M	+S	images	plzák španělský
Camaenidae					
kaménovití					
<i>Fruticicola</i> Held, 1838					
<i>F. fruticum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	keřovka plavá
Helicodontidae					
trojlaločkovití					
<i>Helicodonta</i> A. Férussac, 1821					
<i>H. obvoluta</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	trojlaločka pyskatá
Hygromiidae					
vlahovkovití					
<i>Euomphalia</i> Westerlund, 1889					
<i>E. strigella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	B	M	S	images	keřnatka vrásčitá
<i>Monacha</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>M. cartusiana</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	+B	M	S	images	tmavoretká bělavá
<i>M. claustralis</i> (Rossmässler, 1834) *	+B	–	–	map images	tmavoretká jižní
<i>Trochulus</i> Chemnitz, 1786					

<i>T. hispidus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) *	B	M	S	images	srstnatka chlupatá
<i>T. striolatus danubialis</i> (Clessin, 1874)	–	–	S	map images	srstnatka rýhovaná
<i>T. villosulus</i> (Rossmässler, 1838)	–	M	S	images	srstnatka huňatá
<i>Petasina</i> Beck, 1847					
<i>P. bakowskii</i> (Poliński, 1924)	–	–	S	map images	chlupatka horská
<i>P. bielzi</i> (E. A. Bielz, 1860)	–	–	S	map images	chlupatka východní
<i>P. edentula</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	–	–	map images	chlupatka bezzubá
<i>P. filicina</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1841)	–	–	S	map	chlupatka alpská
<i>P. unidentata</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	B	M	S	images	chlupatka jednozubá
<i>Plicuteria</i> Schileyko, 1978					
<i>P. lubomirski</i> (Ślósarski, 1881)	B	M	S	images	nábělka karpatská
<i>Perforatella</i> Schlüter, 1838					
<i>P. bidentata</i> (Gmelin, 1791)	B	M	S	images	vlahovka lužní
<i>P. dibothrion</i> (E. A. Bielz, 1860) *	–	–	S	map images	vlahovka východní
<i>P. incarnata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) *	B	M	S	images	vlahovka narudlá
<i>P. vicina</i> (Rossmässler, 1842) *	B	M	S	images	vlahovka karpatská
<i>Pseudotrichia</i> Schileyko, 1970					
<i>P. rubiginosa</i> (Rossmässler, 1838)	B	M	S	images	ochlupka rezavá
<i>Urticicola</i> Lindholm, 1927					
<i>U. umbrosus</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	B	M	S	images	žihlobytka stinná
<i>Lozekia</i> Hudec, 1970					
<i>L. transsilvanica</i> (Westerlund, 1876)	–	–	S	map images	vojenka sedmihradská
<i>Hygromia</i> Risso, 1826					
<i>H. cinctella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801) *	+B	–	+S	map images	tenkostěnka kýlnatá
Geomitridae					suchomilkovití
<i>Helicopsis</i> Fitzinger, 1833					

* <i>H. striata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M†	S	map images	suchorypka rýhovaná
<i>Candidula</i> Kobelt, 1871					
<i>C. unifasciata</i> (Poiret, 1801)	B(†)	M	S	images	suchobělka bělavá
<i>Helicella</i> A. Férussac, 1821					
<i>H. itala</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	–	map images	sucholibka ladní
<i>Xerolenta</i> Monterosato, 1892					
<i>X. obvia</i> (Menke, 1828)	B	M	S	images	suchomilka obecná
<i>Cernuella</i> Schlüter, 1838					
<i>C. neglecta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	+B	–	–	images	suchobytká přehlížená
Helicidae					hlemýžďovití
<i>Arianta</i> Turton, 1831					
<i>A. arbustorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	S	images	plamatka lesní
<i>Helicigona</i> A. Férussac, 1821					
<i>H. lapicida</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	B	M	–	images	skalnice kýlnatá
<i>Faustina</i> Kobelt, 1904					
<i>F. cingulella</i> (Rossmässler, 1837)	–	–	S	map images	skalnatka horská
<i>F. faustina</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	B	M	S	images	skalnatka lepá
<i>F. rossmaessleri</i> (L. Pfeiffer, 1848)	–	–	S	map images	skalnatka malá
<i>Isognomostoma</i> Fitzinger, 1833					
<i>I. isognomostomos</i> (Schröter, 1784)	B	M	S	images	zuboústka trojzubá
<i>Causa</i> Schileyko, 1971					
<i>C. holosericea</i> (Studer, 1820)	B	M	S	images	aksamítka sametová
<i>Cepaea</i> Held, 1838					
<i>C. hortensis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	B	M	S	images	páskovka keřová
<i>C. nemoralis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) *	+B	+M	+S	map images	páskovka hajní
<i>Caucasotachea</i> Boettger, 1909					
<i>C. vindobonensis</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828) *	B	M	S	map images	papáskovka žíhaná
<i>Cornu</i> Born, 1778					

C. aspersum (O. F. Müller, 1774) * +B +M +S [map](#) [images](#) hlemýždík kropenatý

Helix Linnaeus, 1758

H. lucorum Linnaeus, 1758 +B – +S [map](#) [images](#) hlemýžd' balkánský

H. lutescens Rossmässler, 1837 – – S [map](#) [images](#) hlemýžd' žlutavý

H. pomatia Linnaeus, 1758 B M S [images](#) hlemýžd' zahradní

H. thessalica Boettger, 1886 * – M S [map](#) [images](#) hlemýžd' pruhovaný

BIVALVIA

mlži

Heteroconchia

Palaeoheterodonta

Unionoida

Margaritiferidae

perlorodkovití

Margaritifera Schumacher, 1815

M. margaritifera (Linnaeus, 1758) B M† – [map](#) [images](#) perlorodka říční

Unionidae

velevrubovití

Unio Philipsson, 1788

U. crassus Philipsson, 1788 B M S [map](#) [images](#) velevrub tupý

U. nanus Lamarck, 1819 * B M? S velevrub malý

U. pictorum (Linnaeus, 1758) B M S [map](#) [images](#) velevrub malířský

U. tumidus Philipsson, 1788 B M S [map](#) [images](#) velevrub nadmutý

Anodonta Lamarck, 1799

A. anatina (Linnaeus, 1758) B M S [map](#) [images](#) škeble říční

A. cygnea (Linnaeus, 1758) B M S [map](#) [images](#) škeble rybníčná

Pseudanodonta Bourguignat, 1877

P. complanata (Rossmässler, 1835) B M S [map](#) [images](#) škeblička plochá

Sinanodonta Modell, 1945

S. woodiana (Lea, 1834) +B +M +S [map](#) [images](#) škeblice asijská

Heterodonta

Veneroida

Corbiculidae

korbikulovití

Corbicula Megerle von
Mühlfeld, 1811

C. fluminea (O. F. Müller,
1774) * +B +M +S [map](#) [images](#) korbikula asijská

Sphaeriidae okružankovití

Sphaerium Scopoli, 1777

S. corneum (Linnaeus, 1758) B M S [images](#) okružanka
rohovitá

S. lacustre (O. F. Müller,
1774) * B M S [images](#) okružanka
rybníčná

S. nucleus (Studer, 1820) B M S [images](#) okružanka
mokřadní

S. rivicola (Lamarck, 1818) B M S [images](#) okružanka říční

S. solidum (Normand, 1844) – – +S [map](#) [images](#) okružanka
žebernatá

Pisidium C. Pfeiffer, 1821

P. amnicum (O. F. Müller,
1774) B M S [images](#) hrachovka říční

Euglesa Jenyns, 1832

E. casertana (Poli, 1791) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
obecná

E. globularis (Clessin, 1873) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
kulovitá

E. henslowana (Sheppard,
1825) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
hrbolatá

E. hibernica (Westerlund,
1894) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
severní

E. milium (Held, 1836) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
prosná

E. nitida (Jenyns, 1832) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka lesklá

E. obtusalis (Lamarck, 1818)
* B M S [images](#) hráškovka tupá

E. personata (Malm, 1855) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
malinká

E. pseudosphaerium (J.
Favre, 1927) * B M S [images](#) hráškovka
okružankovitá

E. subtruncata (Malm, 1855)
* B M S [images](#) hráškovka
otupená

E. supina (A. Schmidt, 1851)
* B M S [images](#) hráškovka
obrácená

Odhneripisidium Kuiper, 1962

O. moitessierianum
(Paladilhe, 1866) * B M S [images](#) hrachovečka
nepatrná

<i>O. tenuilineatum</i> (Stelfox, 1918) *	B	M	S	images	hrachovečka čárkovaná
Dreissenidae					slávičkovití
<i>Dreissena</i> Van Beneden, 1835					
<i>D. polymorpha</i> (Pallas, 1771)	+B	+M	+S	images	slávička mnohotvárná
<i>D. rostriformis</i> (Deshayes, 1838) *	–	–	+S	map images	slávička kvaga

Comment to *Bythinella* species

Bythinella austriaca (von Frauenfeld, 1857) – There are three more species, by their shell morphology similar to *B. austriaca*, reported from Slovakia: *B. hungarica* (Hazay, 1881), *B. metarubra* (Falniowski, 1987) and *B. steffeki* Grego & Glöer, 2019. The latter species has been described based on a single population in the Slovenský kras Mts., the area with frequent occurrence of *B. austriaca*, using only shell and genital morphology. It has been unshakeably proven (e.g. BICHAIN et al. 2007) that classical morphological descriptors may not constitute valid specific criteria within *Bythinella*. Without an integrative taxonomical study, delimiting these putative species based on both mitochondrial and nuclear gene fragments, and without the association of these species with shell morphology, we cannot accept these names as biologically valid taxa. There is no evidence to support an assumption that these species are not only extremes within (eco-)morphological plasticity of a single species, i.e. *B. austriaca*. GREGO & GLÖER (2019) stated: “The COI sequence in the GenBank under number MK673142 indicates a close relation of the new species to some of the *B. austriaca* clades.”, which in other words says that there is no genetic difference (at least based on COI gene) between *B. austriaca* and *B. steffeki*. The phylogenetic analysis published by BENKE et al. (2009) clearly showed that *B. austriaca* and *B. metarubra* are genetically the same.

Comments to species names and new records

Viviparus acerosus Bourguignat, 1862 – for the first time recorded in Bohemia in 2015, see BERAN et al. (2019).

Melanooides tuberculata (O. F. Müller, 1774) – for the first time recorded outdoors in Slovakia in 2000 (MÁJSKY 2000, LIPTÁK et al. 2018). For the first time recorded in Moravia in 2023, see COUFAL & BERAN (2024).

Clathrocaspia knipowitschii (Makarov, 1938) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2019, see SZEKERES et al. (2022).

Hauffenia kissdalmae Eröss & Petró, 2008 – see HAASE et al. (2021).

Hauffenia lozekiana Haase, Grego, Eröss, Farkas & Fehér, 2021 – see HAASE et al. (2021).

Radix lagotis (Schrank, 1803) – for the first records, see ČEJKA et al. (2021). For taxonomy see AKSENOVA et al. (2023).

Ampullaceana ampla (Hartmann, 1821) – for taxonomy see AKSENOVA et al. (2023).

Ampullaceana balthica (Linnaeus, 1758) – for taxonomy see AKSENOVA et al. (2023).

Peregriana peregra (O. F. Müller, 1774) – for taxonomy see AKSENOVA et al. (2023).

Pseudosuccinea columella (Say, 1817) – repeated records from the same outdoor sites between 2013-2016 provide the first evidence of wintering populations in Bohemia (BERAN et al.

2023).

Ladislavella Dybowski, 1913 – originally as *Catascopia* Meier-Brook & Bargues, 2002. Nomenclature follows PIENKOWSKA et al. (2015a) and PIENKOWSKA & LESICKI (2018).

Ladislavella occulta (Jackiewicz, 1959) – European populations were for some time reported under the name *L. terebra* (Westerlund, 1885), see PIENKOWSKA & LESICKI (2018). The first record in Slovakia near the village of Senné (ČEJKA et al. 2020).

Stagnicola palustris (O. F. Müller, 1774) – The molecular data and results presented by PIENKOWSKA et al. (2015a) are insufficiently robust to support the recognition of *Stagnicola turricula* (Held, 1836) as a species distinct from *Stagnicola palustris* (O. F. Müller, 1774). Reliable taxonomic conclusions require evidence from multiple independent nuclear loci. The observed genetic differentiation may instead reflect a distinct mitochondrial lineage within a single, more variable species.

Physa acuta (Draparnaud, 1805) – see comments in WELTER-SCHULTES (2012), p. 56.

Planorbella duryi (Wetherby, 1879) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2023, see ČEJKA et al. (2024).

Gyraulus parvus (Say, 1817) – current genetic investigation revealed that *G. parvus* and *G. laevis* are in fact part of the same species-level clade, with the former having nomenclatural priority (LORENCOVÁ et al. 2021). However, the structure within the mitochondrial tree suggests a North American origin of the invasive populations, earlier reported as *G. parvus*. It also suggests that although the native race in Europe, i.e. *G. laevis*, tend to possess some differences in conchology and ecology, the degree of overlap between the races makes it impossible to accurately distinguish between them without the DNA barcode data.

Gyraulus rossmaessleri (Auerswald, 1852) – the authorship should be ascribed to Auerswald, see BANK (2011).

Ferrissia californica (Rowell, 1863) – originally as *F. fragilis* (Tryon, 1863), see CHRISTENSEN (2016). Sometimes even a month matters in description of a new species.

Pupilla alpicola (Charpentier, 1837) – conspecific with *Pupilla pratensis* (Clessin, 1871), see NEKOLA et al. (2015).

Pupilla sterrii (von Voith, 1840) – the authorship should be ascribed to von Voith, see BANK (2011).

Pyramidula pusilla (Vallot, 1801) – the authorship should be ascribed to Vallot, see BANK (2011).

Pyramidulla saxatilis (Hartmann, 1842) – species resurrected based on DNA from synonymy with *P. rupestris*, but it cannot be differentiated by shell morphology from *P. pusilla*. Only one site has been reported from Veľká Fatra Mts. based on DNA analysis of specimens from that site, see KIRCHNER et al. (2016) and RAZKIN et al. (2016, 2017).

Vallonia pulchella (O. F. Müller, 1774) – based on well-supported genetic and conchological evidence, NEKOLA et al. (2025) synonymized *V. excentrica*, *V. enniensis*, and *V. declivis* with *V. pulchella*.

Vertigo hoppii (Møller, 1842) – HORSÁK et al. (2025) documents that it is conspecific with *Vertigo arctica* (Wallenberg, 1858), which NEKOLA et al. (2018) consider as a separate species, phylogenetically not closely related to *V. modesta* (Say, 1824).

Macrogaster borealis (Boettger, 1878) – Due to some nomenclatorial issues (see <http://www.animalbase.uni-goettingen.de/zooweb/servlet/AnimalBase/home/speciestaxon?>

[id=15626](#)) the well-known name *Macrogastra latestriata* (Schmidt, 1857) had to be substituted by *M. borealis* (Boettger, 1878).

Lucilla scintilla (R. T. Lowe, 1852) – for the first time recorded in Moravia near Mikulčice in 2014, L. Polášek lgt., M. Horsák det. et coll.

Gonyodiscus Fitzinger, 1833 – nomenclature follows SALVADOR et al. (2023).

Gonyodiscus perspectivus (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1816) – *Discus perspectivus* (Megerle von Mühlfeld, 1816) was moved to the genus *Gonyodiscus* Fitzinger, 1833, see SALVADOR et al. (2023).

Gonyodiscus rotundatus (O. F. Müller, 1774) – *Discus rotundatus* (O. F. Müller, 1774) was moved to the genus *Gonyodiscus* Fitzinger, 1833, see SALVADOR et al. (2023).

Perpolita H. B. Baker, 1928 – taxonomy and nomenclature follows SAITO et al. (2024).

Perpolita hammonis (Strøm, 1765) – taxonomy and nomenclature follows SAITO et al. (2024).

Perpolita petronella (L. Pfeiffer, 1853) – taxonomy and nomenclature follows SAITO et al. (2024).

Perpolita radiatella hesperia Saito & Nekola, 2025 – it was elevated to valid species in 2024 (SAITO et al. 2024). Its presence was confirmed from Bohemia, Moravia, Slovakia. It was changed to newly described subspecies from *P. radiatella* (Reinhardt, 1877) to *P. radiatella hesperia* Saito & Nekola, 2025 (SAITO et al. 2025).

Euconulus alderi (J. E. Gray, 1840) [syn. *E. praticola* (Reinhardt, 1883)] – taxonomy and nomenclature follow HORSÁKOVÁ et al. (2020).

Tandonia kusceri (H. Wagner, 1931) and *T. rustica* (Millet, 1843) – see KORÁBEK et al. (2016a).

Deroceras invadens Reise, Hutchinson, Schunack & Schlitt, 2011 – for the first time recorded in Bohemia in 2014, see HUTCHINSON et al. (2014); and in Slovakia in 2017, see ČEJKA (2018).

Deroceras juranum Wüthrich, 1993 – see HUTCHINSON & REISE (2009).

Krynickillus melanocephalus Kaleniczenko, 1851 – for the first time recorded outdoors in Slovakia in 2020, see ČEJKA et al. (2021). For the first time recorded in Bohemia in 2024, see ČEJKA et al. (2025). For the first time recorded in Moravia in 2025, see ŘIHOVÁ et al. (2026).

Ambigolimax valentianus (Férussac, 1822) – for the first time recorded outdoors in Slovakia in 2020, see ČEJKA et al. (2021). Originally as *Lehmannia* Heynemann, 1863, for the current genus assignment see NITZ (2013) and ROWSON et al. (2014).

Limacus maculatus (Kaleniczenko, 1851) – for the first time recorded in Moravia in 2019, see ČEJKA et al. (2020).

Lehmannia carpatica Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022 – originally reported as *L. nyctelia* (Bourguignat, 1861) and later also as *Ambigolimax nyctelius* (Bourguignat, 1861); see NITZ (2013) and ROWSON et al. (2014) for details. HUTCHINSON et al. (2022) noted that the name *L. nyctelia* (Bourguignat, 1861) was used for five different species and raised the new name for the Carpathian populations as *L. carpatica*, since the original name *Limax nyctelius*, based on the Algerian material, is now to be known as *Letourneuxia nyctelia* (Bourguignat, 1861).

Arion intermedius Normand, 1852 – for the first time recorded outdoors in Slovakia in 2020, see ČEJKA et al. (2021).

Monacha claustralis (Rossmässler, 1834) – originally reported as *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu, 1803) by HLAVÁČ & PELTANOVÁ (2010); for further details see PIEŃKOWSKA et al. (2015b).

Trochulus hispidus (Linnaeus, 1758) – *T. sericeus* (Draparnaud, 1801) was confirmed to be a part of phenotypic and genetic plasticity, now being recognized as a younger synonym of *T. hispidus*, see PROČKÓW et al. (2017).

Perforatella dibothrion (E. A. Bielz, 1860) – *Helix dibothrion* E. A. Bielz, 1860 is a conserved name by HAUSDORF (2019).

Perforatella incarnata (O. F. Müller, 1774) – *Monachoides incarnatus* (O. F. Müller, 1774) was moved to the genus *Perforatella* Schlüter, 1838, see ADAMCOVÁ et al. (2024).

Perforatella vicina (Rossmässler, 1842) – *Monachoides vicinus* (Rossmässler, 1842) was moved to the genus *Perforatella* Schlüter, 1838, see ADAMCOVÁ et al. (2024).

Hygromia cinctella (Draparnaud, 1801) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2015, see ČEJKA (2015a) and KRUMPÁLOVÁ & HOLIENKOVÁ (2018).

Helicopsis striata (O. F. Müller, 1774) – a viable population was found in Prague, see PODROUŽKOVÁ et al. (2021).

Cepaea nemoralis (Linnaeus, 1758) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2015, see ČEJKA (2015a) and KRUMPÁLOVÁ & HOLIENKOVÁ (2018).

Caucasotachea vindobonensis (C. Pfeiffer, 1828) – see NEIBER et al. (2016).

Cornu aspersum (O. F. Müller, 1774) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2015, see ČEJKA (2015b). For the first time recorded in Moravia in 2020, see ČEJKA et al. (2021).

Helix thessalica Boettger, 1886 – see KORÁBEK et al. (2016b).

Unio nanus Lamarck, 1819 – see LOPES-LIMA et al. (2024). *Unio nanus* was not confirmed in Moravia yet.

Corbicula fluminea (O. F. Müller, 1774) – for the first time recorded in Moravia in 2018, see KOMZÁK et al. (2018).

Sphaerium lacustre (O. F. Müller, 1774) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa casertana (Poli, 1791) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa globularis (Clessin, 1873) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa henslowana (Sheppard, 1825) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa hibernica (Westerlund, 1894) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa milium (Held, 1836) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa nitida (Jenyns, 1832) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa obtusalis (Lamarck, 1818) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa personata (Malm, 1855) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa pseudosphaerium (J. Favre, 1927) – the authorship should be ascribed to Favre, see BANK (2011). See BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa subtruncata (Malm, 1855) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Euglesa supina (A. Schmidt, 1851) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Odhneripisidium moitessierianum (Paladilhe, 1866) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Odhneripisidium tenuilineatum (Stelfox, 1918) – see BESPALAYA et al. (2023).

Dreissena rostriformis (Deshayes, 1838) – for the first time recorded in Slovakia in 2013 (ČEJKA et al. 2020).

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